

1 **Therapeutic targeting in HER2+ breast cancer to prevent and treat CNS disease: EAF2.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Treatments targeted toward HER2+ breast cancers are limited (1-4). Unbiased discovery approaches
7 have the potential to illuminate subtype-specific vulnerabilities. We performed whole transcriptome
8 differential gene expression analysis of primary tumors of the breast from patients with HER2+ breast
9 cancer, as compared to primary tumors of the breast from patients with breast cancer of other PAM50
10 molecular subtypes: luminal A, luminal B, basal and normal-like, using published microarray data (5-7).
11 We discovered differential expression of EAF2 in human HER2+ breast cancer. EAF2 mRNA was present
12 in higher quantities in tumors of the breast from patients with HER2+ breast cancer as compared to
13 primary tumors of the breast from patients with basal and luminal subtype breast cancers. EAF2
14 expression and function is likely informative in providing some level of molecular description of the HER2+
15 subtype; EAF2 is a candidate molecule in a targeted therapeutics approach in HER2+ breast cancer.
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

CRISPR-based reverse genetic screening of human HER2+ organoids or primary tumor cells freshly isolated from patients with HER2+ breast cancer with limited exposure to artificial culture conditions have not yet been described (8, 9). These genetic technologies, though not yet implemented, when done so will likely facilitate discovery of therapeutic vulnerabilities in HER2+ disease with rapidity and ease. Management of major public health problems requires research (bench)-based management in the short run and long run (10). One example of such a major problem is CNS metastasis in HER2+ breast cancer (11-14): this is a type of cancer that affects a human sex with relatively high frequency, a subtype of that cancer that is diagnosed in approximately one quarter of patients diagnosed with that cancer, and a specific complication of the subtype that develops in half of affected patients.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with breast cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and therapeutic limitations are best managed using identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome differential expression analyses (subtraction analysis), and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully complemented by reverse genetic screening strategies to blindly identify disease-specific, subtype-specific and metastasis-specific therapeutic vulnerabilities augmented by novel immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe one such target identified through rigorous study of the HER2+ tumor transcriptome: a gene product up-regulated, differentially expressed and subtype-specific: EAF2.

Results

Figure 1: EAF2 is differentially expressed in HER2+ breast cancer.

I. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: HER2+ subtype

n=10 primary tumors (breast; human; HER2+)

n=85 primary tumors (breast; human; non-HER2+ subtype, including basal and luminal A/B)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
A_23_P252201	1.76E-05	4.5136532	2.711401	1.55786402	EAF2	51/31157	99.8

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with HER2+ breast cancer, we discovered differential expression of endothelial cell adhesion molecule, encoded by *EAF2* in HER2+ breast cancer in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of *EAF2* changed more than 99% of the human breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 31,157 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the positive fold-change indicating increased quantity of *EAF2* messenger RNA in HER2+ subtype tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of *EAF2* during transformation-specific lineage specification of the breast to the HER2+ breast cancer subtype.

II. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: HER2+ subtype

n=18 primary tumors (breast; human; non-HER2+ subtype: basal, luminal A/B and normal)

n=105 primary tumors (breast; human; HER2+)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8082003	2.14E-06	4.9725066	4.66568	0.83956272	EAF2	133/33297	99.6

1 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with HER2+
2 breast cancers relative to primary tumors of non-HER2+ subtype (including basal, luminal A, luminal B and
3 normal), in a second microarray dataset (6) from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort,
4 we validated differential expression of EAF2 in HER2+ breast cancer in humans (**Chart 2**). The
5 expression of EAF2 here changed more than 99% of the human breast tumor transcriptome when
6 considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 33,297 transcripts ("Rank").
7 Note the positive fold-change indicating increased quantity of EAF2 messenger RNA in HER2+ subtype
8 tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of EAF2 during transformation-specific lineage specification of the
9 breast to the HER2+ breast cancer subtype.

10 Thus, differential and increased expression of EAF2 defines the transcriptional landscape of the
11 HER2+ breast cancer subtype in humans.

12 **Discussion**

13 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
14 treatment with a second treatment (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
15 trastuzumab). Immunoglobulin-based inhibitors of EAF2, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can
16 immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with HER2+ metastasis, with the goal of identifying the most
17 effective reagents for management of HER2+ disease in humans and utilizing these adjunctive agents
18 early in disease to prevent rather than treat CNS disease. We recently used primary tumor transcriptome
19 data to identify multiple phosphatases that we deemed candidate therapeutic targets in management of
20 breast cancer, and fortuitously found their decreased expression was specifically linked to superior overall
21 survival in patients with HER2+ breast cancer (15, 16). A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction
22 with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the
23 spindle at anaphase, in conjunction with activators of the cyclin dependent kinase inhibitors *CDKN* and
24 inhibitors of multi-drug resistance ATP-binding cassette pump genes in resistant cases, is most likely to be
25 most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (17).
26
27
28

References

1. Murthy, R.K., Loi, S., Okines, A., Paplomata, E., Hamilton, E., Hurvitz, S.A., Lin, N.U., Borges, V., Abramson, V., Anders, C. and Bedard, P.L., 2020. Tucatinib, trastuzumab, and capecitabine for HER2-positive metastatic breast cancer. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 382(7), pp.597-609.
2. Stavrou, E., Winer, E.P. and Lin, N.U., 2021. How we treat HER2-positive brain metastases. *ESMO open*, 6(5), p.100256.
3. Kay, C., Martínez-Pérez, C., Meehan, J., Gray, M., Webber, V., Dixon, J.M. and Turnbull, A.K., 2021. Current trends in the treatment of HR+/HER2+ breast cancer. *Future Oncology*, 17(13), pp.1665-1681.
4. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Increased rate of CNS metastasis in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is a result of the intrinsic gene expression program of HER2+ subtype breast cancers, not a consequence of use of the HER2+-targeted drug trastuzumab.
5. GSE87049: Romero-Cordoba, S.L., Salido-Guadarrama, I., Rebollar-Vega, R., Bautista-Piña, V., Dominguez-Reyes, C., Tenorio-Torres, A., Villegas-Carlos, F., Fernández López, J.C., Uribe-Figueroa, L., Alfaro-Ruiz, L. and Hidalgo-Miranda, A., 2021. Comprehensive omic characterization of breast cancer in Mexican-Hispanic women. *Nature communications*, 12(1), pp.1-1.
6. GSE158309: Heimes, A.S., Härtner, F., Almstedt, K., Krajnak, S., Lebrecht, A., Battista, M.J., Edlund, K., Brenner, W., Hasenburg, A., Sahin, U. and Gehrman, M., 2020. Prognostic significance of interferon- γ and its signaling pathway in early breast cancer depends on the molecular subtypes. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 21(19), p.7178.
7. GSE74667: She, Q.B., Gruvberger-Saal, S.K., Maurer, M., Chen, Y., Jumppanen, M., Su, T., Dendy, M., Lau, Y.K.I., Memeo, L., Horlings, H.M. and van de Vijver, M.J., 2016. Integrated molecular pathway analysis informs a synergistic combination therapy targeting PTEN/PI3K and EGFR pathways for basal-like breast cancer. *BMC cancer*, 16, pp.1-16.
8. Koike-Yusa, H., Li, Y., Tan, E.P., Velasco-Herrera, M.D.C. and Yusa, K., 2014. Genome-wide recessive genetic screening in mammalian cells with a lentiviral CRISPR-guide RNA library. *Nature biotechnology*, 32(3), pp.267-273.
9. Shah, A.N., Davey, C.F., Whitebirch, A.C., Miller, A.C. and Moens, C.B., 2015. Rapid reverse genetic screening using CRISPR in zebrafish. *Nature methods*, 12(6), pp.535-540.
10. Pan, A., Liu, L., Wang, C., Guo, H., Hao, X., Wang, Q., Huang, J., He, N., Yu, H., Lin, X. and Wei, S., 2020. Association of public health interventions with the epidemiology of the COVID-19 outbreak in Wuhan, China. *Jama*, 323(19), pp.1915-1923.
11. Lin, N.U. and Winer, E.P., 2007. Brain metastases: the HER2 paradigm. *Clinical Cancer Research*, 13(6), pp.1648-1655.
12. Ponzoni, O., Antonelli, G., Martinelli, G., Baglio, F., Zaniboni, S., Canino, F., Barbolini, M., Molinaro, A., Moscetti, L., Piacentini, F. and Dominici, M., 2024. 208P Clinicopathological factors and treatment management in HER2+ breast cancer patients with central nervous system metastasis. *ESMO Open*.
13. Nader-Marta, G., Martins-Branco, D. and De Azambuja, E., 2022. How we treat patients with metastatic HER2-positive breast cancer. *ESMO open*, 7(1), p.100343.
14. Leyland-Jones, B., 2009. Human epidermal growth factor receptor 2-positive breast cancer and central nervous system metastases. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 27(31), pp.5278-5286.
15. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. The phosphatase PPP4C is differentially expressed in breast cancer and its expression associates with human survival.
16. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. The phosphatase PLPP2 is differentially expressed in breast cancer and its expression associates with human survival.
17. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Therapeutic targeting of catalytically available solid tumor vulnerabilities in human cancer.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We utilized GSE87049, GSE158309 and GSE74667 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in HER2+ primary tumors from humans with breast cancer, as compared to primary tumors of non-HER2+ subtype using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).